

- Please tell us a bit about your Open Source journey to where you are.

- When in your journey, did you make technical contributions to your project?

[If yes, everything below will be about technical]

[If no contributions were made, ask:

- Did you have any technical/code-related involvement in the project? ]

[If they were never involved in anything technical, then everything below is non-technical]

- In this (OSS part of the) journey, where did you feel you got mentored?

[If yes]

- Was this part of any formal mentoring program?

[IF yes]

- How did it help you as a mentee?
- Is this something that is widely spread in your Project / community?

- Did you get any informal mentoring in your journey?

- Can you give us some examples?
- How did you connect with your mentor?

- Did you informally mentor contributors in your journey?

- How did you connect with them?

- In your experience as a senior contributor how do you think formal and informal mentoring compare, where does one shine vs. other?

- Do you think mentoring is acknowledged in ASF?

- What about informal mentoring?

- What do you think we can do to improve mentoring, especially informal mentoring

Thank you for your time.